

Education Quarterly Reviews

Eriyanti, R. W., Kusumastuti, F., Salahudin, Yumitro, G., Roziqin, A., Dintarini, M., Arrozy, A., Wicaksono, A. P., & Muhibah, S. (2022). Humanistic Literacy: Exploring Education Policies for MBKM (Collegiate Independent Learning) Programs from the Participation of the Academic Community in Indonesia. *Education Quarterly Reviews*, 5(2), 47-58.

ISSN 2621-5799

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1993.05.02.467

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

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Humanistic Literacy: Exploring Education Policies for MBKM (Collegiate Independent Learning) Programs from the Participation of the Academic Community in Indonesia

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Abstract

This paper explores 1) why humanistic literacy is important in welcoming the industrial revolution 4.0, especially in the academic community and 2) how the implementation of MBKM (Collegiate Independent Learning) programs can be the main support in responding to industry 4.0. The purpose of this paper is to illustrate “how” the academic community uses knowledge from humanistic literacy. The study used a sample of 1,753 respondents from the academic community of Universitas Muhammadiyah Malang from December 16 to December 19, 2021 using PISA instruments and UNESCO indicators through Likert scale measurements. We show that humanistic literacy is a knowledge capital for the academic community with scores from respondents at the level of identification (4.3), application (4.22), and reasoning (4.24) that support the academic community for the development of social skills such as collaborative efforts and networking development in producing innovative industrial service products.

Keywords: Academic Community, Humanistic Literacy, MBKM programs

1. Introduction

The industrial revolution 4.0 will bring a higher level of automation and interconnectivity in manufacturing processes. The tools, technology, and machines that will be used are expected to be different from what is utilised today. Production tools in the form of smart machines will coordinate their own manufacturing processes with

mechanization of control from human design thinking that will be applied to products or corporate service systems (Berger, 2016).

The manufacturing industry is currently facing the fourth industrial revolution, better known as industry 4.0, in which one can find an intersection between the 'real' and 'virtual' worlds that need to be connected seamlessly to give rise to what is known as a cyber-physical production system. In effect, traditional manufacturing processes undergo a macro transformation that will change the way companies approach manufacturing (Berger, 2016). This will, in turn, encourage an industrial change.

The adoption of the 4.0 model which causes variations, ranging from the mechanization of smart factories. This mechanization automatically impacts the preparation of human resources to control the system productively in the face of several obstacles in the business ecosystem. Such obstacles include, *first*, virtualization of work processes: the level of use of technologies such as augmented reality, virtual plants (cultivation), and for automated information exchange along with monitoring, control and simulation purposes. The *second* obstacle is the complexity of the supply-chain using digital technology. The *third* obstacle is technological disruption, which refers to the degree of change in the business model and ecosystem with the adoption of the latest technologies such as the internet, 3D printing, and smart grids. The *fourth* challenge is resource efficiency of the core process, which refers to efforts needed to increase resource efficiency and to optimize smart machines in the process of adapting industrial technology. The *fifth* and last challenge is forecasting new frameworks or regulations in developing policies or releasing initiatives to promote the adoption of industrial technology.

The Collegiate Freedom to Learn (*Merdeka Belajar-Kampus Merdeka/ MBKM*) program is part of the Freedom to Learn Policy issued by the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology of the Republic of Indonesia that provides opportunities for students to hone their talents and interests by directly participating in the professional workforce and preparing for their future careers. The industrial world is undergoing rapid changes in the form of a new service system through the internet as well as the financial ecosystem (fintech) and online shopping (e-commerce). In this context, design thinking based on knowledge of humanities is needed because of the interaction between online merchants, customer service, users, and buyers. The basis for the MBKM policy is that field practice activities will be converted into credit hours (*Sistem Kredit Semester/SKS*). The exploration of knowledge and skills through a field practice for more than one semester is based on the link website of Indonesia's Ministry of Education (www.kampusmerdekakemdikbud.go.id).

The sites for this study could be programs outside their department or home university. The academic community is able to obtain knowledge and strategies directly from qualified and reputable partners. The concept of "independence" from this program is that the academic community strives to be independent in their decisions and strategic knowledge to face industrial revolution 4.0 by taking advantage of the various available media in this age of information. New media is a form of design on how to stay in touch with the audience and users. (Sinek, 2009) states this in his philosophical design concept thinking that starts that is referred to as "starts with why?".

The urgency of this study is to describe the interconnection between the natural abilities of the academic community and the prediction of demand from the industrial ecosystem 4.0. Capital knowledge of humanities becomes the central theme, complemented by communicative skills and the ability to create designs. Humanities knowledge, communicative skills, and design knowledge are fundamental to sharpen social skills in the form of team works and collaborative efforts to realise innovative products in the age of industry 4.0.

2. Literature review

2.1 Concept and the Urgency of Humanistic Literacy as well as Digital Aspects

Literacy is defined as the ability to read and write, while humanistic literacy is related to communication skills, critical thinking, collaboration, creativity and innovation. Humanistic literacy is a fundamental or essential issue

to pay attention to. This is because literacy is the most basic ability that needs to be possessed by humans or individuals in living their lives, both personally and socially (Alfin, 2018).

In our society, excellent communication skills have a strong correlation with the ability to build networks and/or collaborate with other individuals or groups. Therefore, humanistic literacy becomes a major aspect that must be possessed as a basis for every individual and can be fulfilled by the individual himself, family, school, and country (Yusup, 2017)

Furthermore, it is necessary to understand that there are several types of literacy. In particular, this study refers to basic literacy as described by the Ministry of Education and Culture through the national literacy movement (<https://gln.kemdikbud.go.id>). There are six types of literacy according to the website, A.I, basic literacy, numerical literacy, scientific literacy, financial literacy, digital literacy, cultural literacy and citizenship. These six types of literacy are the basis for fulfilling humanistic literacy (Masitoh, 2018).

These six types of literacy are the responsibility of citizens as well as the government in an effort to fulfil the national goal. However, an important role is held by formal educational institutions because they are the dominant sector in providing education and humanistic literacy. Improving the quality of education is a basic indicator in this regard. It is also argued that critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and global communication are important competencies in the 21st century.

Formal educational institutions are required to properly prepare students to enter the 21st century (Suyatna, 2017). The purpose of strengthening humanistic literacy is to answer problems, and how to build critical, creative, collaborative, and communicative thinking skills through the learning process in formal institutions. Through strengthening humanistic literacy, we hope that it will be able to have a positive impact in increasing the quality index of human resources (Ramdani, 2021)

Fundamentally, humanistic literacy should be the government's obligation to fulfil and facilitate in addition to literacy that comes from the individual's own will as well as from the environment and family. As the executor of the task of prospering the community, the government should be able to provide formulations and stimuli to the community to grow humanistic literacy indicators (Kurniawan, 2019).

In today's advanced digital technology era, there are many changes and novelties in the patterns of humanistic literacy. The ability to communicate and build collaboration is not only understood simply as applying conventional patterns, but is starting to experience a shift by realizing new, more modern pattern (Naufal, 2019). The change in communication and collaboration patterns must go hand in hand with a high level of humanistic literacy. This is important considering that there are quite a few challenges in dealing with various problems in the modern era. The modern era that presents the progress of information and communication technology that is so massive must be understood in a complex way so as not to fall into the trap of time (Fardiah, 2020).

Studying and understanding humanistic literacy is a complex matter. There are several concepts, perspectives, and indicators in understanding humanistic literacy. Adult humanistic literacy is now developing and has a novelty or what is known as new literacy (Achmad Irwan Hamzani, 2020). This new literacy includes data literacy, technology literacy, and humanistic literacy. In the era of ICT advancement, humanistic literacy must be linear with data literacy and technological literacy. These three literacy categories are basically taught in formal schools, both at the elementary and high school level (Nastiti, 2020). The embodiment of technology, cyberspace, big data, and the like has been a serious challenge for the human generation recently. Therefore, humanistic literacy or new literacy needs to be prioritised and emphasised by all relevant stakeholders so that each individual has the ability to communicate and build networks well in the era of disruption (Lestari, 2018).

Today, easy access to information has become a boomerang in the lives of individuals and groups. Some of the problems in the digital era are the presence of hoaxes and discriminations on digital platforms or spaces. The impact is that there are many internet users who swallow information without filtering them (Widiatmojo, 2020). In order to overcome and minimize said problem, the new literacy or literacy possessed by each individual is the

basic requirement for surfing in the virtual world. This becomes important and can be a wise benchmark in navigating life in the modern era (Ainiyah, 2018).

On the other hand, the presence of digital technology has had a huge impact on influencing the pattern of human social life. If in the conventional era an individual could only build communication and networks in the real world, now humans can communicate, through the ease of access offered by the internet and digital platforms, and gather together virtually (Murwani, 2012). Communities in technological advancements can also more easily and freely express their aspirations and build as well as mobilise the masses in virtual spaces. This is certainly a positive value brought by the development of ICT for people's lives, especially in activating democracy. This means that the development must be accompanied by good humanistic literacy, because a good basic understanding of individuals is needed to be able to adapt and develop through the progress of the times especially in the pattern of social life in the digital era (Flew, 2020).

In the current era, the concept of literacy is no longer only associated with information and media. The concept of literacy in this case has been brought into certain parts of human life in a more specific and complex way. With regards to the use of information and communication technology (ICT), for example, literacy is associated with an individual's ability to use computers and the internet on a daily basis (Suri, 2018). Today, literacy has interacted with almost all aspects of human life. The point is that literacy is attached to a lifelong learning process. Individuals who have a strong desire to improve their literacy and abilities will later be able to survive and thrive in navigating life in the world and facing various challenges of the current era. This is indeed the basis because literacy can test and represent an individual's ability to interact with the community and build networks in social life (Yusup, 2017)

Developing and improving humanistic literacy of a country requires cooperation and determination from all parties, from formal educational institutions, government, social / family environment and from within the individuals themselves (Suwardana, 2018). Awareness to meet the needs of humanistic literacy which aims to improve the quality of human resources is an important issue to pay attention to. It is added by considering the many problems and challenges in supporting good humanistic literacy in the era of massive development. So, basically there are several patterns or concepts that can be presented by each element that has been described previously to develop a strong humanistic literacy (Batoebara, 2021).

Next, there are several concepts or patterns that should be implemented to fulfill the indicators of humanistic literacy in order to realize it properly. *First*, it is to provide massive education and information, especially to formal educational institutions, from elementary to upper secondary and tertiary levels. It is very important to pay attention to the improvement of the quality of education (Ainiyah, 2018). *Second*, it is imperative to set the foundation through early education in the primary circle. The primary circle in this case is the family. Family as the first element of individual growth and development can be the primary source in providing literacy and a shield for individuals to be wise in living their lives, both in the real world and virtual world (Batoebara, 2021). *Third*, it is important to massively and periodically filter and publish information and education on various digital platforms. This can be done by the government as the greatest authority in a country. With all the access that they have, the government should have high political will in improving humanistic literacy for its people (Kurniawan, 2019). The point is that all relevant elements or stakeholders in the effort to realize humanistic literacy must be able to collaborate and carry out their respective duties and functions optimally. This is the key to success in fulfilling the indicators of humanistic literacy (Ramdani, 2021)

Below is a table related to the concept and indicators of humanistic literacy that can be carried out as an effort to develop human resources through strengthening humanistic literacy:

Table 1: Concept and Indicator of Humanistic literacy

Humanistic literacy or Communication Skills and Networking or Collaborative Efforts		
No.	Concept	Indicator
1.	Massive education and information in formal education institutions	- Strengthen and improve the quality of education - Cross-check and evaluate educational practices

		- Massively and periodically promote humanistic literacy in educational institutions
2.	Implanting literacy from an early age in the primary circle (family)	- Literacy is introduced early by parents and family - Provide education to parents regarding the pattern of educating/providing literacy in children
3.	Implanting literacy on digital platforms	- Subsidise the provision of information on humanistic literacy culture in various digital/social media platforms - Cancel or terminate access to publications containing discriminations and hoaxes - Provide and guarantee freedom of communication and build networks in digital space/platforms

In order to develop high quality human resources, it is necessary to improve the pattern of humanistic literacy as well. To increase humanistic literacy, we can pay attention to and implement the basic concepts and indicators as mentioned in table 1. The contents of these concepts and indicators are to certainly be carried out by all relevant parties in a country. Thus, if it can be carried out in a collegial collective manner, it is not impossible to strengthen humanistic literacy and make it impact the quality of human resources in such country.

2.2 The Illustration of Humanistic Literacy in the Era of Industry 4.0

The industry 4.0, where the position of the virtual and ‘real’ worlds is connected with the production system of the cyber world, represents a transformative change for business institutions (corporates) and regulators (government) that call for a change of the manufacturing approach from the basis of human resource management. In a global survey conducted by the Roland Berger Consulting Institute (2016) on skill development for the workforce group in the age of industry 4.0, there is a mismatch between the skill sets demanded by the industry and those mastered by job applicants.

When referring to the conceptual approach of humanistic literacy, especially humanistic philosophy, the intersection is in the development of skills on “how to build networks” and collaborative efforts for the individual aspect of students, while the industrial 4.0 orientation requires resource management skills (RMS) in the form of financial and material management, people management, time management, and communication skills. However, to support resource management skills, it is necessary to understand how individuals build their networks. The said social skills are in the form of coordinating with others, negotiation, persuasion, emotional intelligence, directing and teaching others, and service orientation (Berger, 2016).

Possess social skills alone is not enough. It is also necessary to have fundamental backups in managing networks, namely, active listening, critical thinking, and self-monitoring. It is an effort to ensure that students can do collaborative work by maximising teamwork to produce product designs that are accepted by the business ecosystem.

The collaborative effort aims to improve students in design thinking which includes the use of logic, imagination for illustration, intuition, and systemic reasoning. Design thinking elaborates rational thinking with intuitive thinking. This is based on the concept of design intelligence that the system needs to solve a problem by understanding the rapidly changing situation (Simon, 1985).

(Simon, 1985) distinguishes analytical thinking (which results in breaking down ideas) from design thinking (which results in ideas). Ultimately, what we need is the abductive reasoning, a reasoning that prioritizes simplification in order to solve problems with simple methods. Design thinking requires four simple points:

1. Empathy: How to see the world from another person's point of view, not just seeing it from an individual perspective.
2. Optimism: Efforts to ensure that there is the best solution to a problem.

3. Experiment: The audacity to try new things, including the courage to fail and learn from failure.
4. Collaboration: Always looking for opportunities to collaborate with others, to get the most optimal results.

The stages of implementing design thinking are (1) defining the problem, (2) determining solution options from various perspectives, (3) creating prototypes accompanied by a commitment to improve, and (4) constantly iterating solutions along with efforts to improve the most needed design constructions.

Design thinking is an important basis for humanistic literacy to support student skills in building networks and collaborative efforts. In the Guide to the Preparation of the Higher Education Curriculum in the Era of Industry 4.0 by the General Directorate of Higher Education within the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia, it is stated that humanistic literacy is an understanding of humanities, and communication by design. This is indeed prioritised to improve students' social skills with each student group making collaborative efforts aimed at producing product designs for industrial purposes.

Strengthening design thinking requires variables from the conception of humanities knowledge, which are ethics, art history, philosophy, media studies, cultural anthropology, and art performance (Rens, 2013). In the field of communication, one needs journalism, public relations, interpersonal, news, and marketing studies (Ferguson, 2014). Meanwhile, in design, we need social media toolkit, frame analysis, figure analysis, the grammar of design, and motion picture (Cross, 1982).

Networking for students is nothing but self-management related to increasing social capital (Putnam, 2000). From social-capital bonding which starts from strong social ties to the alma mater, public-good model, and inward looking which then transforms to bridging social capital that is outward looking and the ideas can be accepted by various people with different backgrounds (Claridge, 2018).

Humanistic literacy aims to increase the active participation of individuals to involve themselves in certain phenomena and react to them in their own way (Sari, 2020). Strengthening humanistic literacy is nothing but honing social skills as reflected in the Indonesian education philosophy, namely solidarity and collaboration (known as the concept of "*gotong-royong*" in Indonesian), anti-discrimination, dialogue, inclusivity, and integrity.

3. Research methods

The research was conducted using a field survey, the data was analysed quantitatively with rapid analysis following the data collection procedure for the participation of the academic community. The research instrument was compiled through the process of compiling a grid based on the measured literacy aspect and the literacy level referring to the PISA model (Suprayitno, 2018).

There were "statement" and "question" questionnaire items that the respondent needed to answer. Next, we inputted these questions and statements results into a Google Form practical instrument. The questionnaire was measured using a Likert scale with various statements from 1 to 5 referring to the "Global Framework of Reference on Digital Literacy Skills: Skills for Indicator 4.4.2" (UNESCO, 2018). 1 = totally disagree 2 = disagree 3 = not sure 4 = agree 5 = totally agree.

The key elements of humanistic literacy include social, physical, intellectual, cultural, and emotional (S.P.I.C.E). The online questionnaire was conducted among 35,000 academics, specifically the undergraduate program at the Universitas Muhammadiyah Malang, Indonesia. The participants were told that the goal is to investigate the tools used for the involvement of the academic community in online education during the transition from physical to distance learning (hybrid learning as class method).

Questionnaires were administered to the academic community, using a Google form, with multiple choice questions. For these students, as well as for most of the lecturers, this is the first time they are fully involved in

online education without any offline meetings. In a pandemic situation, the distribution of lecture materials, assignments, and tutorials is carried out through a learning link management system built on the concept of “student centred learning” (SCL) (www.lms.umm.ac.id).

The results of our research are several variables, which indicate the participation of the academic community at Campus Three of Universitas Muhammadiyah Malang. To keep track of the increase in identification, researchers used instruments for probability (Aassve, 2012). Quantitative description model was carried out with Likert scale instrument (Allen, 2007). It has been estimated by researchers that data from 7 faculties (Psychology, Islamic Religion, Economics, Social Sciences, Education, Agriculture and Engineering) were taken through an online sample involving 1,753 respondents, it averages 5% of the entire population through nonparametric quantitative descriptions.

4. Results

The research location is Campus Three of Universitas Muhammadiyah Malang, which is a sub-urban campus located 8.7 km from the downtown of Malang. This campus is located in the Subdistrict of Dau at Jl. Tlogomas No. 246. According to the archives of the Directorate General of Higher Education in 1966 based on Decree Number 68/B-Swt/p/1966 Campus Three of UMM consists of 7 faculties covering 26 undergraduate programs (bachelor degree).

At the beginning of the picture of the participation of academia community related to human literacy questionnaire shows aspects of S.P.I.C.E in the following bar diagram: notes in Bahasa term identification (*identifikasi*), implementation (*penerapan*), and reasoning (*penalaran*).

Description of civitas academia participation in the form of gender based on the results of data retrieval:

Table 2: The level of human literacy based on gender

Literacy Aspect	Gender	Identification	Category	Implement	Category	Reasoning	Category
Socially	Men	4.010229	good	4.398902	good	4.152335	good
	Women	3.954244	fair	4.474286	good	4.103826	good
Intellectually	Men	4.027156	good	4.28613	good	4.17599	good
	Women	4.025534	good	4.365608	good	4.198225	good
Culturally	Men	4.129951	good	4.28507	good	4.310222	good
	Women	4.170913	good	4.288947	good	4.191777	good
Emotionally	Men	4.469618	good	4.364876	good	4.326543	good
	Women	4.417043	good	4.427283	good	4.333653	good
Physically	Men	4.341494	good	4.190748	good	4.211792	good
	Women	4.359061	good	4.240143	good	4.276942	good

Note. in Bahasa term good (*baik*) and fair (*sedang*)

The exploration of knowledge capital and capabilities in the field during the online learning period results in the following information. According to PISA, the stages of literacy includes: 1) identification, 2) implementation, and 3) reasoning. According to this standard, the scores of literacy among the academic community in the 26 study programs are as follows: identification (4.3), implementation (4.22), and reasoning (4.24).

Figure 1: Human Sosial Literacy Level

The social aspect score is considered to provide opportunities for the development of the social skills of the academic community for network building and collaborative efforts (Sari, 2020). Network building requires reading of humanistic literacy from respondents in the form of emotional aspects that support individual traits, with each score per faculty, which are: identification (4.41), implementation (4.39), and reasoning (4.31).

Figure 2: Human Emotional Literacy Level

Data collection is based on a sample of faculties in viewing humanistic literacy using Likert scale. We begin to discuss the empirical results by first showing several tables of quantitative descriptions of the participation of the academic community by seven faculties, then presented in the two tables. The tables show the level of participation of the academic community for the sample used in the estimation of 1,753 respondents.

Table 3: Participation of the academic community socially

Socially						
Faculty	Identific- -ation	Category	Implement- -ation	Category	Reasoning	Category
(1)Economy and Business	3.92	Fair	4.43	Good	4.08	Good
(2)Psychology	3.91	Fair	4.39	Good	4.03	Good
(3)Islam	3.63	Fair	4.71	Good	4.52	Good
(4)Social and Political Sciences	4.04	Good	4.44	Good	4.10	Good
(5)Education	3.97	Fair	4.57	Good	4.15	Good
(6)Agriculture	4.01	Good	4.38	Good	4.26	Good
(7)Engineering	3.75	Fair	4.16	Good	3.88	Fair

Table 4: Participation of the academic community emotionally

Emotionally						
Faculty	Identific- -ation	Category	Implement- -ation	Category	Reasoning	Category
(1)Economy and Business	4.41	Good	4.38	Good	4.34	Good
(2)Psychology	4.20	Good	4.15	Good	4.12	Good
(3)Islam	4.40	Good	4.19	Good	4.62	Good
(4)Social and Political Sciences	4.25	Good	4.13	Good	4.16	Good
(5)Education	4.50	Good	4.32	Good	4.36	Good
(6)Agriculture	4.35	Good	4.40	Good	4.39	Good
(1)Economy and Business	4.52	Good	4.27	Good	4.36	Good

The hypotheses related to humanistic literacy are as follows: H0; There is no difference in the average humanistic literacy between students who have participated in MBKM programs and those who have not participated in the MBKM programs.

H1; There is a difference in the average humanistic literacy between students who have participated in MBKM programs and those who have not. Quantification of each faculty provides an overview of the level of participation and percentage of the academic community, with a pie chart as follows:

Figure 3: Humanistic Literacy response

The responses from the academic community regarding the identification questionnaire shows that identification is 32%, implementation is 32%, and reasoning is 33%. This is related to the actualization of “student centred learning” which is the basis for MBKM policies to anticipate the age of industry 4.0. Then the participation of academia community related to the level of human literacy based on regional origin in Indonesia:

Table 5: Human literacy based on regional origin in Indonesia

Literacy Aspect	Region	Identification	Category	Applied	Category	Reasoning	Category
Socially	Bali	3.77	Fair	4.41	Good	4.02	Good
	Jawa	4.06	Good	4.52	Good	4.17	Good
	Kalimantan	3.84	Fair	4.39	Good	4.00	Fair
	Maluku	4.06	Good	4.51	Good	4.12	Good
	Nusa Tenggara	4.04	Good	4.47	Good	4.24	Good
	Papua	3.63	Fair	4.48	Good	4.14	Good
	Sulawesi	3.92	Fair	4.68	Good	3.86	Fair
	Sumatra	3.97	Good	4.30	Good	3.95	Fair
Emotionally	Bali	4.33	Good	4.42	Good	4.28	good
	Jawa	4.59	Good	4.42	Good	4.38	good
	Kalimantan	4.38	Good	4.39	Good	4.26	good
	Maluku	4.42	Good	4.50	Good	4.21	good
	Nusa Tenggara	4.46	Good	4.42	Good	4.41	good
	Papua	4.49	Good	3.92	Fair	4.17	good
	Sulawesi	4.32	Good	4.46	good	4.56	good
	Sumatra	4.46	Good	4.27	good	4.17	good

5. Discussion

As a comparison from the findings of Naufal's previous study (2019), there has been a realization of a new, more actual pattern in the context of modernity. In the point of view of this study, the content of social skills is based on the emotional aspect of humanistic literacy that produces empathy. Empathy is the foundation of the academic community's ability to develop social skills that are oriented towards networking and collaborative efforts.

The development of empathy in the individual and social circles requires experimentation on taking new patterns from the achievements of the academic community. The knowledge capital obtained from access to humanistic literacy and the knowledge of humanities as well as communication is expected to create expressions of humanistic value in various individual statements in the context of social media accounts, especially promoting product knowledge and team-performance to the audience.

Experimentation in the teamwork among the academic community is individual as well social character building through collaborative efforts, especially the division of roles based on teamwork. In the concept of bridging social capital, this argument can improve managerial actions in building teamwork relations so that they can recognize “people who are different” and are inclusive and outward looking (Claridge, 2018)

The relationship between the development of the academic community in the concept of “student centred learning” places individuals in teamwork based on humanistic literacy in line with placing emotions into empathy and constructive reasoning. Emotion and empathy are based on moral development whose reasoning process is based on humanistic literacy. Humanistic literacy can function as a parameter for the development of individual morality on how to evaluate scientific and artistic works related to design thinking.

Humanistic literacy can serve as a reference for the academic community both as individuals and as a community that need to have “motivated goals” and for designing them with peers. The concepts offered by Kohlberg's (2009) moral development and Putnam's (2000) social capital in the development of collaboration are based on the homogeneity of information, new ideas, and behaviour patterns towards team-work relations by negotiating with the audience or structural ties.

If the linear conception of Kohlberg (2009) is applied, the moral development process is based on individual reasoning processes based on relational exchanges related to regulatory systems and social order construction. In moral development, the construction of a social contract determines the universal ethical principle based on access to humanistic literacy.

6. Conclusion

The results of data collection indicate that the level of humanistic literacy in the academic community of Universitas Muhammadiyah Malang requires individual strengthening which is useful for networking and collaborative efforts. This matter requires the adoption of the concept of “student-centred learning” which is promoted by the MBKM policy with the consequence of a reasoning rate of 33%. Reasoning in the form of quantitative reasoning, logic, empathy, and communication skills are a form of individual strengthening for the academic community to convey work designs or study products, which is parallel with the opportunities for collaborative efforts.

7. Acknowledgments

Thank you to the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia and the University of Muhammadiyah Malang.

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